

PNDP Instantons in Two Dimensions

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Abstract

In this paper, we extend the PNDP braneworld scenario by introducing σ -torsors, a topological invariant of the spinor bundle. We investigate instantons in two-dimensional conformal field theory using the $CFT_d \leftrightarrow \mathcal{AdS}_{d+1}$ correspondence.

1 Introduction

In the Pigazzini-Pinčak braneworld scenario, there exists a class of manifolds, so-called “type II *PNDP* manifolds, which have an equal number of fiber dimensions and virtual dimensions. These cancel out and leave us with a point-like topological manifold. The ramifications of considering this seep into almost every aspect of physics; for instance, *emerging* or *dark sector* models seem to arise somewhat miraculously when one considers Penrose-type singularities to be spaces possessing intrinsic $U(n)$ symmetries.

These manifolds are of the form:

$$B \times_f F \cong *$$

where the volume-form of $*$ is given by:

$$Vol_* = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} Vol_B^{-n/2} \times_f Vol_F^{n/2} \quad (1.1)$$

when we have $\dim_{\mathbb{R}} B = n$.

This is, of course, considering that the point $*$ is embedded in a spacetime $\mathcal{M}^d$ which is Ricci flat and has a trivial obstruction bundle. In order to modify (1.1) for curved spacetime patches, i.e. spaces that are not Cat_0 , we need to essentially pull-back the metric over $\mathcal{M}^d$ to a disjoint union of locally flat spaces:

$$\varphi^*(\mathcal{M}^d) = \left(\mathcal{M}_{pre}^{d/2} \sqcup \mathcal{M}_{pre}^{d/2} \right) \oplus E$$

where E is the obstruction bundle. If d is even, then E is again trivial, and we obtain a lift:

$$\begin{array}{ccc}
 & \text{string}_{d-1} & \\
 & \uparrow & \\
 & \text{spin}_d & \text{string}_d \\
 & \uparrow & \uparrow \\
 * & \longrightarrow \mathcal{L} & \longrightarrow \mathcal{M}
 \end{array}$$

from a unique Lagrangian submanifold $\mathcal{L} \subset \mathcal{M}$ to a $\mathbf{string}_{d-1}$ -structure. If d is odd, i.e., we have $d \equiv 1$ when we mod by 2, then we obtain a *central extension* of our algebra. In conformal field theory, this means that we pass from the *Witt algebra* to the *Virasoro algebra*. We refer the reader to Haine’s exposition on this topic for further debriefing.

2 σ -torsors

Suppose we are given a collection of spinor fields $\phi_0, \dots, \phi_n$. We can then proceed to construct a *spinor bundle* Φ as follows. We start with a generic fiber bundle $\mathcal{P}$, whose total space is our choice of Σ -model, and whose base space is either $\mathcal{L}$ or $\mathcal{M}$. Then, we take the sheaf of global sections of $\mathcal{P}$ (which we will denote by Γ), and equip each $\gamma_q \in \Gamma$ with a spinor field ϕ_q . Following Witten [3], the action for a generic ϕ_q reads:

$$\mathcal{S}(\phi_q) = \frac{1}{2 \cdot q!} d^n x \sqrt{g} e^{\gamma/(q+1)} + F \text{ terms} \quad (2.1)$$

Now, in the spirit of Grothendieck, we want some sort of “inverse image functor;”

$$\boxed{\mathcal{P}^*(\phi_q) = s^{-1}(\gamma_q)} \quad (2.2)$$

which sends the q th section of our spinor bundle back to the original Σ -manifold. This has the effect of modifying our co-ordinates as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma &\longmapsto \frac{1}{n} \ker \mathcal{S}(\phi_q) \\ \tau &\longmapsto \frac{1}{n} \exp((q+1)/\gamma) \end{aligned}$$

In the case our target manifold is properly *PNDP*, we have to consider the influence of the virtual dimensions. Suppose that they parameterize our co-ordinates like so:

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{PNDP} &= |\sigma\rangle \left\langle \frac{1}{\sigma_{vir}} \right| \\ \tau_{PNDP} &= |\tau\rangle \left\langle \frac{1}{\tau_{vir}} \right| \end{aligned}$$

Then, we have to restrict ourselves to a choice of symmetrization; i.e., a mapping

$$\bullet_{vir} \longmapsto \mathbf{Poly}_\bullet$$

from the virtual portion of the *PNDP* to the category of polynomials of equal order to $\bullet$. In one time dimension and three spacial dimensions; i.e., for the lightcone $\mathbb{L}^4 \cong Sp(4)/K$, these maps look like:

$$\sigma_{vir} \longmapsto -a^2 \sigma^3 - a \sigma^2 - \sigma$$

and

$$\tau_{vir} \longmapsto -\tau$$

So, the formal sum of vector bundles:

$$B \times_{\tau} F = 0 \simeq *$$

holds. We can interpret this as a $\frac{1}{4}$ BPS state. On the other hand, we obtain for the spacial co-ordinates

$$B \times_{\sigma} F = -a^2 \sigma^3 - a \sigma^2$$

giving us

$$\boxed{\left(B \times_{\sigma} F \right) // (a \sigma^2) = \mathbb{1}^{\vee} (a \sigma + \sigma)} \quad (2.3)$$

where $\mathbb{1}$ is the identity matrix.

Clearly, if $\sigma = 0$, then a *PNDP* manifold parameterized uniquely by σ and τ will become completely a lightlike singlet. Suppose we are interested in a “background-free” formulation of a given string theory. Then, what we are looking for is a (p, q) -string model that contains σ -torsors.

2.1 $n = 2$

To explain the notion of a σ -torsor, suppose we are given a p -brane $\mathcal{B}$ (for concreteness, an AdS_3 brane), satisfying:

$$T(\mathcal{B}) = (g_{\mu\nu} x_{\mu} g_{\mu\nu} x^{\nu})^n + F(\tau) \quad (2.4)$$

with

$$F(\tau) = \left(F_{n^2}(\tau) \circ F_{n^2-1}(\tau) \dots \circ F_0 \right) \quad (2.5)$$

Define:

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_L &= g_{\mu\nu} x_{\mu} \\ \sigma_R &= g_{\mu\nu} x^{\nu} \end{aligned}$$

Definition 2.1. A σ -torsor (in two dimensions) is a pair of sections $(L\gamma, \gamma_R) \in \Gamma$ equipped with a symmetric bi-linear form $\star$ such that:

- $L\gamma \star \gamma_R = \gamma_R \star L\gamma$
- For every pair of extensors $\mathcal{P}$ and $\mathcal{Q}$, and for some 1-form A_0 , we have:

$$\left(\mathcal{P}(L\gamma) \right) \star \left(\mathcal{Q}(\gamma_R) \right) = A_0 \cdot \sigma_L \sigma_R \quad (2.6)$$

such that

$$\int A_0 \cdot \sigma_L \sigma_R = A_1 \cdot \frac{1}{2} (\sigma_R \sigma_L)^2 \quad (2.7)$$

where

$$A_1 = \omega \star \sigma$$

We need to recall the definition of an extensor now.

Definition 2.2. Let $\alpha > 0$. Let $\partial\mathcal{B}$ be the brane boundary. Let Vol_x be the volume form on an object $x \in \mathcal{B}$. Let $\beta = Vol_{\mathcal{B}}$. Then, an extensor on x is defined as

$$X = \alpha Vol_x < \beta$$

In this case, ω is a standard *symplectic form*; it satisfies:

$$\omega = dA_0 \wedge d\tau = -d\tau \wedge dA_0$$

Applying definition (2.1) to our spatial co-ordinates yields:

$$B \times_{L\gamma, \gamma_R} F = -a^2(\sigma_L \sigma_R)^3 - a(\sigma_L \sigma_R)^2 \quad (2.8)$$

some basic algebra gives

$$\Omega = \left(B \times \left(\mathcal{P}_{(L\gamma)} \right) \star \left(\mathcal{Q}_{(\gamma_R)} \right) F \right) // (a\sigma^2) = A_0 \times \mathbb{1}^\vee (a\sigma^2 + \sigma^2) \quad (2.9)$$

and we get

$$\int \Omega = A_1 \cdot \frac{1}{2} \left((\sigma_R \sigma_L)^2 \right) + a\sigma^2 + \frac{1}{2}\sigma^2 \quad (2.10)$$

Setting

$$\Omega = \frac{1}{2 \cdot q!} d^n x \sqrt{g} e^{\gamma/(q+1)} \quad (2.11)$$

we get

$$\mathcal{S}(\phi_q) = \Omega + \left({}_L\gamma \star F(\tau) \star \gamma_R \right) \quad (2.12)$$

and so we see plainly that our σ -torsor depends solely on our choice of $F(\tau)$.

2.1.1 AdS_3

The effect of introducing a σ -torsor into a representation of an AdS_3 brane is that Poincaré symmetry (that is to say, $SL(2, Z)$ symmetry) is preserved across the entire worldsheet of a string. That is, if the x we used in (2.2) is a Polchinski-type instanton¹, then we have:

$$\int_{\partial\mathcal{B}} \gamma_q \simeq \int_{\mathcal{B}'} X \quad (2.13)$$

In the Wess-Zumino-Witten (WZW) model used in [3], the AdS -brane cuts through the AdS_3 brane. Specifically, when one sets

$$AdS_3 \cong S^2$$

a type II $PNDP$ manifold $*$ can then be adjoined anywhere on the sphere to recreate the Hilbert sphere.

¹That is to say, a $p = 0$ - brane.

Recollection 2.1. *The Hilbert n -sphere*

$$\mathbb{S}_{Hilb}^n$$

is a topological manifold equipped with one singularity, $\hat{b}$, which represents a rational point at infinity.

We can express the winding number of the AdS_3 brane with respect to $\hat{b}$, or, more generally, with respect to a preferred instanton colinear with $\hat{b}$. Our σ -torsor essentially acts as a “forgetful functor” from the Fukaya category $\text{Fuk}_{\hat{b}=0}$ to the category $\text{Fuk}_{\hat{b}\simeq*}$. The map

$$\mathcal{E}_* : \text{Fuk}_* \longrightarrow \text{Fuk}_0$$

is called the *Emmerson-Fukaya functor*, and it has a left adjoint:

$$\mathcal{E}^* : \text{Fuk}_0 \longrightarrow \text{Fuk}_*$$

Together, they fit into the following diagram:

$$\begin{array}{ccc} \mathbb{E} & \begin{array}{c} \longleftarrow \\ \longrightarrow \end{array} & \mathbb{R} \\ \downarrow & & \downarrow \\ \text{Fuk}_* & \begin{array}{c} \xleftarrow{\mathcal{E}^*} \\ \xrightarrow{\mathcal{E}_*} \end{array} & \text{Fuk}_0 \\ \downarrow & & \downarrow \\ * & \begin{array}{c} \longleftarrow \\ \longrightarrow \end{array} & 0 \end{array}$$

where the vertical morphisms are given by descending to subobjects.

Under toroidal compactification, our AdS_2 brane becomes an instanton; denote it by $\mathcal{B}_{inst}$. A σ -torsor acts on the instanton like this: suppose we have a formal product:

$$B \times_f F = \mathcal{B}_{inst} \tag{2.14}$$

Then, for a “good” (path-connected, locally contractible) neighborhood around the instanton, we obtain:

$$\int_{\partial AdS_3} \mathcal{S}(\phi_q) \simeq \int_{AdS_2} C \Omega \tag{2.15}$$

where we set

$$C = \int_{L\gamma}^{\gamma_R} w \tag{2.16}$$

where $w > 0$ is the winding number of the string around $\hat{b}$. From (2.12) this gives us

$$\int_{\partial AdS_3} \mathcal{S}(\phi_q) \simeq \int_{AdS_2} \left(\mathcal{S}(\phi_q) - \left({}_{L\gamma} \star F(\tau) \star \gamma_R \right) \cdot \left(\int_{L\gamma}^{\gamma_R} w \right) \right) \tag{2.17}$$

By (2.13) this gives us:

$$\mathcal{S}(\phi_q) - \left({}_{L\gamma} \star F(\tau) \star \gamma_R \right) \cdot \left(\int_{L\gamma}^{\gamma_R} w \right) < \beta \tag{2.18}$$

which means

$$\left(\int_{\partial AdS_2} C\Omega \right) - \gamma_q = - \left({}_L\gamma \star F(\tau) \star \gamma_R \right) \cdot \left(\int_{{}_L\gamma}^{\gamma_R} w \right) \ll \beta \quad (2.19)$$

so that we can write

$$\mathcal{B} = \gamma_q \otimes X \oplus E \quad (2.20)$$

giving us

$$Vol_{\mathcal{B}_{int}} = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} Vol_X^{-n/2} \times_E Vol_{\gamma_q}^n \quad (2.21)$$

where

$$\gamma_q = {}_L\gamma \star \gamma_R$$

A References

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